

Youth-oriented Active Labour Market Policies: Explaining Policy Effort in the Nordic and the Baltic States

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Abstract

The starting point of this study is the seemingly striking similarity in the number of youth-oriented labour market policies adopted by the Nordic and the Baltic EU member states in 2013–14 despite markedly different welfare regimes. The similarities remain when concentrating on active labour market policies (ALMPs) and extending the observation period to 2007–15, but the application of a more refined coding scheme suggests that there are also notable cross-country differences. Estonia, Finland and Sweden are found to exhibit a relatively similar approach to youth-oriented ALMPs, while Denmark, Latvia and Lithuania are more distinct cases. The similarities in the policy effort can be explained by similar problem pressure, EU-guided policy learning and the provision of EU funding. Lastly, the policy approaches of the Nordic states indicate a path-dependency. Thus, while the youth-oriented policy effort may appear to be quite similar, important differences remain.

Keywords

Active labour market policies; European Youth Guarantee; Youth unemployment; Welfare regimes

Introduction

Over the course of the last three decades, youth unemployment in the EU has been double or even triple the rate of general unemployment (cf. Cinalli and Giugni 2013; Lahusen *et al.* 2013; O'Reilly *et al.* 2015; Marques and Salavisa 2016; Tosun *et al.* 2016; Tosun 2017). Consequently, the adoption of policy measures focusing on this target group was given high priority. Youth-oriented active labour market policies (ALMPs) are prominent examples of such policy measures. Generally speaking, ALMPs consist of a

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diverse set of policy tools covering education and training, subsidized employment, and labour market services (Armingeon 2007; Bonoli 2010; Nelson 2013; Bengtsson 2014; Hörisch and Weber 2014).

Many EU member states have decades-long experience with ALMPs. Denmark and Sweden were among the first countries to embrace ALMPs (Eichhorst and Konle-Seidl 2008; Bengtsson 2014), soon followed by Finland (Kananen 2012). In 2007, Denmark, Finland and Sweden – along with France – were also the countries with the highest public expenditures on ALMPs (Martin 2015: 4). A further commonality found in Denmark, Finland and Sweden is their ‘social democratic’ welfare regime (Esping-Andersen 1990; for a discussion, cf. Cox 2004; Jochem 2011; Kvist and Greve 2011; Kananen 2012; Béland *et al.* 2014; Marques and Salavisa 2016). This is important to mention, as welfare regimes have been found to be key in determining whether and which types of ALMP approaches policymakers adopt (cf. van Vliet 2010; Nelson 2013; Starke *et al.* 2014).

Against this background, it comes as no surprise that the Nordic countries have recently adopted an increased number of specifically youth-oriented ALMPs (cf. Olofsson and Wadensjö 2012). This country group has a great deal of experience with ALMPs and it thus seems logical that it would also rely on this approach in tackling youth unemployment. What is, however, surprising is that in a recent report published by the European Commission, the Nordic countries were indicated to have adopted the same number of ‘youth-oriented reforms’ as the Baltic states.

The Baltic states are a group of countries with significantly less experience with ALMPs than the Nordic states and that have a ‘former-USSR’ type welfare regime that resembles the conservative welfare regimes, but with lower public spending levels than the Western European types (Fenger 2007: 24; Aidukaite 2009; Toots and Bachmann 2010). According to the data presented in the report, in 2013 and 2014 there were three ‘youth-oriented reforms’ in Denmark, two in Finland and seven in Sweden, compared to two in Estonia, seven in Latvia and three in Lithuania (European Commission 2016a: 24–5). To be sure, the figures given in the report include both ALMPs and non-ALMPs targeting the youth. Nevertheless, the similarity in the number of policies adopted can be regarded as an empirical puzzle that warrants further attention.

To this end, we pose three research questions that guide this study. First, we wish to know whether the similarity in the ‘youth-oriented reforms’ persists when concentrating exclusively on ALMPs, but in an extended observation period. Second, we are interested in how similar the youth-oriented ALMPs are when applying a more refined coding scheme. Third, how can we explain the similarities in the policy effort between the Nordic and the Baltic countries?

The remainder of this study unfolds as follows. The next section provides details on ALMPs, which is followed by the presentation of our theoretical considerations and the formulation of hypotheses. The subsequent section clarifies the research design and the measurement of the variables. We then present and discuss the empirical findings before providing some concluding remarks. Overall, we observe more similarity between the two country groups in the number than in the types of youth-oriented ALMPs adopted.

Types of Active Labour Market Policies

Despite originating in Northern Europe, ALMPs have been adopted by a growing number of countries across Europe. The diffusion of ALMPs can be explained by their two-dimensional character: they foster investments in knowledge, skills and training, while at the same time also focus on strengthening work incentives (Bengtsson 2014: S56). In other words, there is a demanding side and an enabling side to ALMPs (Eichhorst and Konle-Seidl 2008: 5), which makes them, in principle, appealing to policymakers in both liberal and conservative welfare regimes. The demanding elements are thought to align with the ideology of policymakers in liberal regimes, whereas policymakers in conservative welfare regimes also find them appealing, as they offer social security 'without necessarily resorting to redistributive measures and without changing established social hierarchies' (Armingeon 2007: 907).

Several international organizations have been eager to promote ALMPs, including the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the EU (cf. van Vliet 2010; Cinalli and Giugni 2013; Lahusen *et al.* 2013; Hörisch and Weber 2014; Martin 2015), but the degree to which ALMPs have actually been embraced varies. Armingeon (2007) shows that the liberal welfare states in the OECD did not take up this policy idea as eagerly as the conservative welfare states; concentrating on the EU, van Vliet (2010), however, reports that conservative welfare regimes make less use of ALMPs than liberal and social democratic welfare regimes. Moreover, according to Nelson (2013), ALMPs represent a distinct feature of the social democratic welfare regime. Thus, despite the two-dimensional character of ALMPs, their appeal seems to depend on the welfare regimes, with the Nordic states being most favourable towards them.

For a better understanding of the political economy of ALMPs, Bonoli (2010) proposes differentiating ALMPs along two further dimensions: pro-market employment orientation and investment in human capital. Pro-market employment orientation refers to whether the policy measures place individuals in non-subsidized jobs in the private or public sector. Investment in human capital concerns the extent to which policies correspond to a low-investment workfare orientation – that is, tougher requirements for those receiving social benefits (cf. Kananen 2012) – or a high-investment orientation to reintegrate the unemployed into the labour market.

Based on these two dimensions, Bonoli (2010) identifies four types of ALMPs. The first type, *incentive reinforcement*, refers to strengthening positive and negative work incentives for people on benefits (strong pro-market employment orientation; strong workfare orientation). The second type is *employment assistance* and includes placement services, job coaching as well as job subsidies (strong pro-market employment orientation; strong workfare orientation). *Occupation*, the third form, consists of measures such as job creation schemes to keep jobless people active and to prevent the depletion of human capital (weak pro-market employment orientation; strong workfare orientation). The fourth form, *human capital investment*, is about providing basic

education and vocational training to jobless people (strong pro-market employment orientation; strong human capital investment).

Reviewing the literature on youth-oriented ALMPs, Caliendo and Schmidl (2016) also distinguish between different types. The first is *labour market training*, which refers to measures aimed at extending or adapting the labour market relevant skill set of participants. The second type is *job search assistance and monitoring*, which comprises counselling and mentoring activities by public employment services or other providers. The primary focus of these measures is to increase the commitment and motivation of job search activities among youth. The measures are accompanied by higher intensity support and are also linked to higher levels of monitoring, often in combination with implicit or explicit threats of benefit sanctioning. The third type refers to *wage subsidies*, that is, financial incentives for employers to hire young jobseekers. Fourth, ALMPs for young people may consist of *public sector work programmes*, which are usually temporary state-funded employment opportunities in the public sector or in areas that help to produce socially valuable goods or services. The objective of these programmes is to provide young people with employment opportunities and work experience.

The ALMP-types identified above can be easily combined. *Human capital investment* (Bonoli 2010) represents a category in and of itself, as does *labour market training* (Caliendo and Schmidl 2016). *Job search assistance and monitoring* (Caliendo and Schmidl 2016) corresponds to *incentive reinforcement and employment assistance* (Bonoli 2010). *Wage subsidies* (Caliendo and Schmidl 2016) are a refinement of *employment assistance* (Bonoli 2010). *Occupation* (Bonoli 2010) corresponds to *public sector employment programmes* (Caliendo and Schmidl 2016). We return to these categories in the methodology section.

Theoretical Considerations and Hypotheses

The Nordic and the Baltic states are different with regard to the history of the development of their welfare systems and the level of public spending on social policy. The Nordic states have a long-established history of ALMPs (Armingeon 2007; van Vliet 2010; Nelson 2013; Bengtsson 2014) and have generous welfare arrangements corresponding to the social democratic model (Esping-Andersen 1990). The Baltic states, on the other hand, have far less experience with ALMPs (Martin 2015) and have less generous welfare arrangements corresponding to the ‘former-USSR type’ model (Fenger 2007). Despite these differences, a recent report published by the European Commission (2016a) suggests a striking degree of similarity in ‘youth-oriented reforms’. How can we explain this similarity?

Armingeon (2007: 911–12) gives several possible explanations for the design of ALMPs, including path-dependency (cf. Pierson 2000; Cox 2004; Jensen 2009), the acceptability of policies on ideological grounds (cf. Nelson 2013; Starke *et al.* 2014), the initiation or adjustment costs incurring from ALMPs (cf. Graziano 2011), and re-election considerations in combination with high levels of problem pressure (cf. Jensen *et al.* 2014). Of these factors, we do not focus on the acceptability of policies on ideological grounds, since

this would warrant a different research design (cf. Armingeon 2007; Nelson 2013; Hörisch and Weber 2014; Jensen *et al.* 2014; Starke *et al.* 2014).

High levels of problem pressure are likely to induce governments to adopt policy measures irrespective of existing policy arrangements and corresponding initiation costs (cf. Jensen 2009). In the case at hand, a sharp increase in youth unemployment as well as the continuation of high levels of youth unemployment can be considered as problem pressure that induces policymakers to act. This reasoning leads to the formulation of our first hypothesis:

H1: A similar degree of problem pressure results in similar policy effort.

As stated above, youth unemployment has not only affected the countries examined here. In response to the soaring levels of youth unemployment across Europe, the European Youth Guarantee (EYG) was adopted in 2013, which calls on the member states to adopt measures to ensure that young people get a 'good quality' offer for a job, an apprenticeship, a traineeship, or continued education within four months of leaving education or becoming unemployed (O'Reilly *et al.* 2015; Tosun 2017). To deliver the EYG, the member state governments need to effectively adopt youth-oriented ALMPs (cf. Lahusen *et al.* 2013; Escudero and López Mourelo 2015). From this, it follows that the need to comply with the EYG may have brought about similarities in policy effort.

There are two ways in which the adoption of the EYG could have affected the relevant policy decisions taken by the Nordic and the Baltic states. The first mechanism is the transposition and application of binding European law, which in the present case, however, is hampered by the fact that the EU only published guidelines and not exact rules for how the EYG should be implemented (cf. European Commission 2016b). What the European Commission does is to regularly review and assess the policy measures adopted by the individual member states (cf. European Commission 2016a, 2016b). This suggests that policy learning, the second mechanism, is more likely to be relevant.

Policy learning takes place in two ways. First, the EU has identified some member states to serve as models for learning about how to design their policy measures to implement the EYG, including the role of ALMPs. Interestingly enough, Finland was identified as such a model from which the other EU member states should learn (European Commission 2014). This corresponds to learning through benchmarking, as practiced for many years in the field of European employment and social policy by means of the Open Method of Coordination (OMC) (cf. Zeitlin *et al.* 2005; Radaelli 2008). Second, the regular review of policy effort is likely to stimulate policy learning on the basis of a member state's own past policy performance (cf. Eichhorst and Konle-Seidl 2008). This reasoning culminates in the second hypothesis, which summarizes both types of policy learning:

H2: EU-guided policy learning results in similar policy effort.

A third factor that may explain the similarity in policy effort is also related to the EU, but to a different mechanism. In marked contrast to previous employment policies that were based on the OMC, the policy regime aiming to foster youth employment is accompanied by funding schemes (Chabanet 2014; Tosun *et al.* 2016; Tosun 2017). Since ALMPs – especially the ones focused on human capital investment – entail costs (cf. Bonoli 2010; Nelson 2013), it is plausible that the provision of funding plays a role in triggering similar policy effort. However, this effect should concern the countries with lower initial budgets, as they obtain new room for manoeuvre with the additional funding provided by the EU. Therefore, hypothesis 3 reads as follows:

H3: Provision of funding for states with lower budgets will result in convergence in policy effort with states with higher budgets.

So far, we have not discussed the role of path-dependency, as this factor is more suitable for explaining differences rather than similarities. Yet path-dependency may play a role when we more systematically differentiate between the ALMP types as they are influenced by established welfare regimes (cf. Nelson 2013). Therefore, the fourth hypothesis reads as follows:

H4: Past policy decisions determine the types of new policies adopted.

Methodology and Measurement

The objective of this study is to examine whether exposure to problem pressure, EU-guided learning, availability of EU funding, and path-dependency matter for explaining the adoption of youth-oriented ALMPs. Problem pressure, EU-guided learning and availability of EU funding are closely interlinked, thereby rendering it difficult to test the hypothesized effects independently. We can nevertheless illustrate the plausibility of the individual explanatory factors identified. In order to disentangle these factors to at least minimal degree, we begin our analysis in 2007 – the year in which the economic and financial crisis began and youth unemployment saw a precipitous rise. We interpret the policy effort made in 2007–09 as relatively independent responses by the individual countries to problem pressure.

As concerns EU-guided learning, we expect this factor to have come to the fore from 2010 and in particular from 2013 onwards. In 2010, the European Commission called on the member states to establish the EYG and put forward a corresponding proposal. However, it was only in April 2013 that the Council of the EU adopted the proposal (Escudero and López Mourello 2015: 2–4). Therefore, youth-oriented ALMPs adopted after 2010 are likely to have been affected by EU-guided learning processes.

To facilitate the implementation of the EYG, the EU created a new financial instrument: the Youth Employment Initiative (YEI) with a budget of €6.4 billion for the period 2014–20 (Chabanet 2014). Funding from the YEI was only allocated to regions in member states where youth

unemployment was higher than 25 per cent in 2012 (Tosun *et al.* 2016; Tosun 2017). Even earlier in 2011, the Youth Opportunities Initiative allowed the member states' governments to make increased use of the European Social Fund (ESF) for promoting youth employment (O'Reilly *et al.* 2015: 9). Consequently, the member states could rely on EU funding to invest in ALMPs from 2011 onwards.

Regarding path-dependency, the analyses of the ALMP types adopted will show to what extent they correspond to the measures that were in place in 2007, that is, before youth unemployment soared due to the crisis (cf. Jochem 2011).

Table I reports public expenditures on general – not youth-specific – ALMPs (% of gross domestic product [GDP]) and to which interventions the expenditures were allocated as indicated by Eurostat. As concerns the ALMP types, we must bear in mind that the Eurostat codes do not perfectly align with the categories suggested by Bonoli (2010) and Caliendo and Schmidl (2016). Instead, Eurostat (2013) differentiates between training, employment incentives (abbreviated: 'incentives'), supported employment and rehabilitation ('support'), direct job creation ('job'), and start-up incentives ('start-up').

Table I further reports the share of young people (aged 15–29) neither in employment nor in education or training (NEETs) – in 2007, 2010, 2013 and 2015. We rely on the NEET share rather than on the unemployment rate or ratio to capture the problem pressure since the NEET share indicates inactivity among young people and therefore corresponds more directly to the aims of the EU's policy approach (cf. O'Reilly *et al.* 2015). The four years were selected to capture the initial level of youth unemployment (2007), the level when the European Commission first proposed the adoption of the EYG (2010) and the level when the EYG was formally adopted (2013). The NEET rates in 2015 indicate what the problem pressure was like at the end of the observation period. Lastly, the allocation of funding from the YEI and ESF (the EU contribution only) are reported.

The dependent variables of this study are the number and types of youth-oriented ALMPs adopted in the period 2007–15. The data for the period 2007–14 is extracted from the LABREF database, which is a publicly available inventory of labour market reforms in the EU maintained by the European Commission. The data for the year 2015 is taken from the respective country reports prepared by the European Commission and checked by means of information provided on the websites of the corresponding national ministries. Further details on the data sources and coding of the dependent variable can be found in the Supporting Information (see below).

We use the categories proposed by Caliendo and Schmidl (2016) with the exception of human capital investment, which is a category proposed by Bonoli (2010). Moreover, we added two further categories:

- Human capital investment (i.e. basic education and vocational training).
- Labour market training (i.e. temporary programmes to improve relevant skills).

Table I
Country profiles

	Denmark	Finland	Sweden	Estonia	Latvia	Lithuania
ALMP 2007	0.98	0.68	0.77	0.02	0.10	0.22
ALMP 2013 (change)	1.34 (0.36)	0.86 (0.18)	1.07 (0.3)	0.13 (0.11)	0.19 (0.09)	0.19 (-0.03)
ALMP type 2007 (share)	Support (0.55) Training (0.33) Incentive (0.12)	Training (0.53) Incentive (0.19) Support (0.13) Direct (0.12) Start-up (0.03)	Incentive (0.62) Support (0.22) Training (0.14) Start-up (0.02)	Training (0.90) Start-up (0.05) Incentive (0.05)	Training (0.44) Incentive (0.37) Job (0.12) Start-up (0.07)	Training (0.40) Incentive (0.28) Support (0.23) Job (0.09)
NEETs 2007	3.4	5.2	4.1	8.3	10.3	7.7
NEETs 2010 (change)	3.8 (0.4)	6.1 (0.9)	4.2 (0.1)	7.4 (-0.9)	8.4 (-1.9)	6.3 (-1.4)
NEETs 2013 (change)	4.7 (0.9)	6.4 (0.3)	4.1 (-0.1)	8.3 (0.9)	8.0 (-0.4)	6.4 (0.1)
NEETs 2015 (change)	4.9 (0.2)	6.9 (0.5)	4.0 (-0.1)	8.6 (0.3)	7.4 (-0.6)	6.2 (-0.2)
YEI	-	-	44,163,096	-	29,010,639	31,782,633
ESF	254,788,619	618,564,064	691,551,158	391,517,329	583,103,717	1,028,306,727

Notes and sources: ALMP expenditures (% GDP; Eurostat code: tps00076; categories 2-7); ALMP type according to Eurostat (2013) (Eurostat code: tps00077); NEET rate (15-29 years; in %; Eurostat code: yth_empl_150); YEI = Youth Employment Initiative (source: http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-15-4101_en.htm); ESF = European Social Fund (source: <http://ec.europa.eu/esf/main.jsp?catId=574&langId=en>); funding period 2007-13; EU contribution only.

- Job search assistance and monitoring (i.e. counselling and mentoring to increase the commitment and motivation of job search, including benefit sanctioning).
- Wage subsidies (i.e. subsidized wages or income support schemes).
- Public sector employment programmes (i.e. state-funded temporary employment opportunities).
- Packages (i.e. a combination of at least two different policy types).
- Other (i.e. a policy measure that cannot be assigned to any of the above categories).

Empirical Findings

In this section, we first examine the policy effort of the Nordic states and then turn to the Baltic states and the comparative discussion of the findings in light of the theoretical considerations.

Policy effort in the Nordic states

In *Denmark*, the first relevant policy measure was adopted in 2008 and addressed providing guidance to young people who did not complete upper secondary education (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 1). In the same year, the government made it obligatory for 10th grade students to choose at least two different education programmes (*other*; 2).

In 2011, a *package* (3) of four policy measures was adopted, which primarily aimed to increase the number of unemployed youth in training, to strengthen their skill development, and to give unemployed graduates access to the labour market. In the same year, a second *package* (4) of six measures was adopted, including the possibility to engage in an 'upgrading of skills job', targeted training, strengthened effort towards unemployed academics, job rotation arrangements, courses in basic education, and an increased number of work-experience placements and traineeships. Furthermore, funds were allocated to create additional apprenticeships and traineeships in vocational schools (*human capital investment*; 5). In 2012, the initiative 'building a bridge to education' (*package*; 6) and a measure to increase the access of vocational students to traineeships were adopted (*human capital investment*; 7).

In 2013, the government decided to increase the quality of vocational education and to increase the proportion of the youth cohort in vocational schools (*human capital investment*; 8). In June 2014, the parliament passed a vocational education and training system reform with the goal of offering high-quality programmes and good opportunities for further education and training (*human capital investment*; 9).

Altogether, the measures adopted in Denmark concentrate almost exclusively on human capital investment, which is also reflected in the policy packages that combine human capital investment with labour market training.

The first policy measure adopted in *Finland* in 2008 ensured expanding on-the-job-training and apprenticeships (*labour market training*; 1). In the same

year, *wage subsidies* (2) for the apprenticeship training were increased and the threshold for receiving these was lowered. In 2009, eligibility for *wage subsidies* (3) was further lightened for young jobseekers.

In 2010, an employment voucher to subsidize full-time employment for vocational education graduates was introduced (*wage subsidies*; 4). The 'apprenticeship experiment' adopted in 2012 aims at making apprenticeship training more accessible for both trainees and employers (*labour market training*; 5). Even more interesting is the reformed youth guarantee, which enhances services for young people under 25 and strengthens the obligations for young jobseekers to be active themselves (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 6). Also in 2012, a special education programme was adopted (*human capital investment*; 7).

In 2013, the Finnish government introduced an education guarantee (*human capital investment*; 8), followed by the launch of one-stop shops in 35 municipalities, which aim to strengthen and simplify services for young people (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 9). Taken together, the Finnish policy effort shows a good balance of human capital investment, labour market training, job search assistance and monitoring, and wage subsidies.

In *Sweden*, changes to the job guarantee were made in 2007 that consisted of job search assistance and monitoring as well as labour market training (*package*; 1). In 2009, a subsidy scheme for hiring long-term unemployment was adopted (*wage subsidies*; 2).

In 2010, several measures were adopted: An extension of coaching support to young people (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 3), a 'youth agreement' to create a 'vocational introduction employment' scheme for the industry (*labour market training*; 4), and a temporary increase in secondary adult vocational education programmes (*human capital investment*; 5). In 2012, the government extended and raised the provider allowances for apprentices (*wage subsidies*; 6). In the same year, the 'youth package' was adopted, which, *inter alia*, encompasses investments in apprenticeship education (*package*; 7).

In 2013, measures to support employers hiring young people in jobs where training is combined with work were adopted (*wage subsidies*; 8). In 2014, the government introduced upper secondary apprentice employment as a new employment form (*labour market training*; 9). Moreover, *wage subsidies* for employers were introduced (10). The government also strengthened case handling by the public employment service (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 11). The government also adopted the 90-day guarantee of education or employment (Wadensjö 2015), which is designed to further strengthen early intervention by increasing the number of support offers made within the first months of unemployment (*package*; 12).

The Swedish policy approach is quite diverse, but when taking a closer look at the policy packages, it places substantial emphasis on wage subsidies along with human capital investment and labour market training.

Policy effort in the Baltic states

The first youth-oriented ALMP in *Estonia* falling into our observation period is the 2009 programme for apprenticeship training for young people (*labour market training*; 1). In 2010, a temporary ease in the eligibility for *wage subsidies*

(2), a programme to create training opportunities for school dropouts to complete their studies (*human capital investment*; 3), and a temporary employment programme that expanded a range of ALMPs to young jobseekers (*package*; 4) were adopted. In 2011, the eligibility for grant benefits was expanded to people falling under the 2010 temporary employment programme (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 5).

In 2014, a measure on organizing job search workshops was adopted (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 6) along with the ‘my first job’ scheme, which introduced *wage subsidies* (7) and reimbursement of employers’ training costs. The quantity of Estonian policy effort is relatively small, but the ALMPs adopted are quite diverse (cf. Government of Estonia 2009: 19–20).

In 2010, *Latvian* policymakers introduced internships at the State Employment Agency (*public sector work programme*; 1), supported voluntary work in non-governmental organizations (*public sector work programme*; 2), and agreed on the organization of workshops at educational institutes to give young jobseekers the opportunity to experiment with different professions (*labour market training*; 3).

In 2011, the ‘work places for young people’ programme introduced subsidized private sector jobs for youth (*wage subsidies*; 4). In the same year, support for young unemployed doing volunteer work (*public sector work programme*; 5) and a voucher to participate in vocational training, requalification, qualification improvement and non-formal training programmes were adopted (*labour market training*; 6).

In 2012, additional internship places were offered at the State Employment Agency (*public sector work programme*; 7) together with the provision of additional funding for professional training (*human capital investment*; 8). Moreover, a scheme was introduced to provide opportunities for young jobseekers to try out different jobs at a vocational training institution (*labour market training*; 9).

In 2013, the internship scheme at the State Employment Agency was extended by one year (*public sector work programme*; 10). A measure offering young jobseekers more targeted support was also adopted (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 11). Eleven modernized vocational education and training competence centres were set up (*human capital investment*; 12). In 2014, subsidized workplaces for disadvantaged young people were created (*wage subsidies*; 13). Moreover, profiling and individual actions for outreach were adopted (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 14). Young people with a higher or vocational education degree and who are not full-time students were offered the opportunity to acquire initial work experience (*labour market training*; 15). The legislative amendments in 2015 introduced work-based learning as one type of acquiring vocational education and training (*other*; 16).

Latvia adopted the greatest number of ALMPs, which range from human capital investment to public sector work programmes. To be sure, the latter, together with labour market training, represent the dominant youth-oriented ALMP types.

In *Lithuania*, the ‘first job programme’ was launched in 2007 to help young jobseekers in finding their first job (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 1). In 2010, the government introduced increased *wage subsidies* (2) for employers

hiring young people. Moreover, sectoral practical training centres within the vocational education system were opened (*human capital investment*; 3). In 2011, the scheme ‘support for the first job’ was adopted, which consists of a subsidy to the employers (*wage subsidies*; 4). In 2012, the project ‘increasing youth employment’ was launched, which is also a *wage subsidy* (5).

In 2013, a programme for the intensive and long-term assistance for unemployed and school drop-outs was adopted (*job search assistance and monitoring*; 6). In 2014, the possibility to do voluntary traineeships was introduced and persons completing a voluntary traineeship were to be granted social guarantees (*labour market training*; 7). Moreover, the ‘agreement for the acquisition of professional skills’ was adopted, according to which young people participating in supported employment measures remain covered by compulsory health insurance by the state for a certain period (*other*; 8). The regulations with respect to work-based vocational training were updated with a view to reducing the vocational grants, while at the same time expanding the eligibility for vocational training to EU citizens and residents (*other*; 9). Lastly, the subsidy rate of training costs in the case of the ‘support for the acquisition of professional skills’ measures were reduced (*other*; 10).

Looking at the policy measures adopted, the Lithuanian approach is also dominated by wage subsidies and job search assistance and monitoring. Yet it should be noted that quite a few policy decisions cannot be assigned to our coding categories.

Discussion

Table 2 summarizes the policy effort made by the countries and helps to identify similarities and differences. First, all countries have adopted youth-oriented ALMPs in the observation period and most were adopted in 2010–12. Second, all countries have adopted measures aiming at human capital investment and job search assistance and monitoring. Third, packages of policy measures were adopted in Denmark, Sweden and Estonia, indicating that this approach is not limited to either country group. Yet, the composition of the policy packages already displays notable differences: Denmark and Sweden adopted bundles of policies entailing high human capital investment, which does not hold true for the Estonian policy package.

This brings us to differences that exist between and within the country groups. First, Denmark stands out since its ALMPs concentrate heavily on human capital investment. Finland and Sweden are more homogenous in terms of their mix of ALMPs compared to Denmark. Second, Latvia shows two distinguishing features. First, it is the country with the greatest number of policy adoptions; second, the dominant policy instrument is public sector work programmes, which no other state analyzed here adopted during the observation period. Third, Lithuania also appears to be an exceptional case, since its policy measures are not easily assigned to the coding categories derived from Bonoli (2010) and Caliendo and Schmidl (2016). Moreover, the last policy adoption entailed a reduction in the subsidy rate of training costs, which represents an instance of policy dismantling not observed in the other countries examined (cf. Starke 2006; Jensen *et al.* 2014; Zartaloudis 2014).

Table 2

Overview of policy effort, 2007–15

	Denmark	Finland	Sweden	Estonia	Latvia	Lithuania	Σ
Human capital investment	4	2	1	1	2	1	11
Labour market training	0	2	2	1	4	1	10
Job search assistance and monitoring	1	2	2	2	2	2	11
Wage subsidies	0	3	4	2	2	3	12
Public sector work programmes	0	0	0	0	5	0	5
Package	3	0	3	1	0	0	7
Other	1	0	0	0	1	3	5
Effort 2007–09	2	3	2	1	0	1	9
Effort 2010–12	5	4	5	4	9	4	31
Effort 2013–15	2	2	5	2	7	5	23
Σ Effort 2007–15	9	9	12	7	16	10	63

Notes and sources: Own elaboration based on <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/labref/public/> and <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1161&langId=en>. The bold figures signify the most frequently selected type of youth-oriented ALMPs.

Summing up, the empirical picture obtained from concentrating on youth-oriented ALMPs and expanding the observation period supports the initial impression that there exist similarities between the two country groups (cf. European Commission 2016a). When adopting a more refined measurement scheme, we can detect differences in the ALMPs adopted. These differences, however, refer less to the country groups than the individual countries. Denmark has adopted a focused policy approach, whereas Finland and Sweden adopted a broader policy approach. Estonia's approach is relatively similar to that of Finland and Sweden, although Estonia adopted fewer policies focusing on human capital investment. Latvia adopted the greatest number and the most diverse set of ALMPs, combining both high- and low-investment in human capital. The case most difficult to connect to the other countries is Lithuania, as many policy decisions were made that do not correspond to our coding scheme, and also because we could observe an instance of policy dismantling. Generally speaking, there is more similarity across the countries in the quantity than the quality of the policy effort.

In our first hypothesis we postulated that the adoption of youth-oriented ALMPs depends on the degree of problem pressure. More precisely, similar problem pressure should lead to similar policy effort. When looking at the increase in the NEET rates from 2007 to 2009 as shown in table 1, we can see that it was sharper in the Nordic countries, which may explain why these states adopted a greater number of policies in that period than the Baltic countries. There is evidence that the Nordic states discussed the causes of and remedies for youth unemployment at several Nordic Council of Ministers

meetings since 2008 (Djernaes 2013). It is possible to identify a trend of small to moderate reductions in the comparatively higher NEET rates in the Baltic states alongside small to moderate increases in the comparative lower NEET rates in the Nordic countries. The similarity in problem pressure and policy effort lends plausibility to H1.

Turning to the next hypothesis, it is important to note that the greatest number of policy adoptions took place in 2010–12, followed by the 2013–15 period. The European Commission (2014) identified Finland as the country from which the other states should draw lessons. However, the European Commission's Mutual Learning Programme also entails that countries get feedback on their policy arrangements from peers (cf. Radaelli 2008) as well as learn from past policy performance they have taken (cf. Eichhorst and Konle-Seidl 2008).

In 2014, the European Commission (2014) organized a meeting in Helsinki to review the implementation of the Finnish youth guarantee scheme and to draw lessons from it as well as to subject the schemes by the other participating countries to peer review. Delegations from Denmark, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Sweden participated in the event and reviewed the Finnish model as well as received comments on their own policy approaches (European Commission 2014). The peer review of the youth guarantee is just one example of how information about the corresponding policy measures are shared and evaluated. The annual country reports and multi-annual evaluation reports prepared by the European Commission are another venue for EU-guided policy learning (cf. European Commission 2016a, 2016b). From this, it is reasonable to conclude that the similarity in policy effort – which we could actually observe to some degree – stems from EU-guided policy learning.

The YEI and ESF allocations to Latvia and to Lithuania could explain why these countries caught up in terms of their policy effort in the period 2010–15. Estonia did not qualify for YEI funding, but the Estonian government used ESF funding to finance the ALMPs adopted. According to the LABREF database, Estonia used ESF funding for the programme 'increasing the supply of qualified labour force 2010–2011', the organization of job search workshops, and the 'my first job' scheme. Latvia used ESF funding for 'work places for young people programme' and Lithuania for the 'support for the first job' project as well as for the 'increasing youth employment' programme (cf. Supporting Information, see below). These examples show that H3 on the role of funding is plausible, that is, the provision of EU funding provided an incentive to policymakers in the Baltic states to adopt youth-oriented ALMPs (cf. Tosun *et al.* 2016). The Nordic states have more generous budgets and do not depend on EU funding to the same extent as the Baltic states. Nevertheless, even the Finnish government acknowledged the use of ESF funding for establishing one-stop service centres (cf. Supporting Information, see below).

When comparing the general ALMP types in place in 2007 (table I) with the range of the youth-oriented ALMPs adopted, there is some evidence of path-dependency. Finland, Sweden, Latvia and Lithuania had many different ALMP types in place, which corresponds to the many different types of

instruments adopted. In the case of Sweden, we observe continuation with regard to the emphasis placed on employment incentives and wage subsidies (cf. Eurostat 2013: 16), and in the case of Finland as concerns the focus on training. This is different in the cases of Latvia and Lithuania, where the focus on training indicated in table 1 is not reflected in the policy measures adopted. Turning to Denmark, there is continuation in terms of the concentration on some ALMP types. While the category ‘supported employment and rehabilitation’ does not correspond to the data coded in table 2, the importance of training is maintained. Lastly, turning to Estonia, the ALMPs focus on training (accounting for about 90 per cent of the expenditures) is not at all reflected in youth-oriented policies. Summing up, H4 is only supported for the Nordic states.

Conclusion

The objective of this study was to address whether and why the Nordic and Baltic EU member states have made similar policy effort to combat youth unemployment. To this end, we examined in detail different types of youth-oriented ALMPs adopted in the period 2007–15. The empirical analysis revealed that there indeed exist a number of similarities between the two country groups in their policy effort, which can be traced back to the relatively similar problem pressure stemming from youth unemployment, EU-guided learning, and the provision of EU funding, which particularly helped the Baltic states to compensate for their smaller state budgets. Perhaps the most important finding is that in the case of youth-oriented ALMPs EU-guided learning – together with financial support – can lead to similar policy responses. Previous studies concentrating on the use of OMC in employment and social policy were more sceptical about this possibility (cf. Radaelli 2008). Thus, the higher political commitment attached to combatting youth unemployment at the EU level (cf. Chabanet 2014; O’Reilly *et al.* 2015; Tosun 2017) does, indeed, become visible in national policy decisions (cf. Tosun *et al.* 2016).

However, the refined measurement also highlighted differences in the ALMP types adopted by the countries under study. Generally speaking, the policy effort by Estonia, Finland and Sweden is relatively similar, albeit Estonia has adopted fewer policies that entail human capital investment. The policy approaches by Denmark, Latvia and Lithuania are particular, albeit for different reasons. Denmark, which is also particular due to its model of ‘flexicurity’ (cf. Marques and Salavisa 2016), placed great – or in fact almost exclusive – emphasis on human capital investment, whereas Latvia adopted a remarkably broad policy approach, and Lithuania even reduced its expenditures on one policy instrument. These differences, especially among the Nordic states, can at least in part be explained by path-dependent policy decisions.

While this study has provided some important insights, there exist a number of ways in which our understanding can be further improved. There are, for example, numerous alternative explanations that we were not able to consider within the scope of this study. Most importantly, related studies have shown that partisan ideology matters for adopting ALMPs (cf. Nelson 2013;

Hörisch and Weber 2014; Starke *et al.* 2014). A second avenue for future research is to adopt an alternative specification of the dependent variable and to analyze processes of policy change (cf. Hall 1993; Streeck and Thelen 2005) or policy convergence (cf. Armingeon 2007; van Vliet 2010). Adopting the analytical perspective proposed by Streeck and Thelen (2005) appears particularly interesting for a comparison of these two countries groups since we would expect institutional creation in the Baltic countries and institutional change in the Nordic countries. This study has provided some evidence of these processes when we discussed the importance of path-dependency for the focus of the youth-oriented ALMPs in the Nordic countries. An even more rewarding yet also more demanding approach may be to combine policy change with changes in ALMP expenditures (cf. Jensen *et al.* 2014), which would present a third option for subsequent research endeavours. As the policy measures targeting youth unemployment continue to develop, new research perspectives will emerge that can expand on the insights offered here.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information may be found in the online version of this article at the publisher's website:

Table S1 Denmark

Table S2 Estonia

Table S3 Finland

Table S4 Latvia

Table S5 Lithuania

Table S6 Sweden

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